

Lingophilosophical and lingocognitive interpretation of the concept of love in Uzbek and English languages

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Abstract: The significance of the lingo-philosophical and lingo-cognitive interpretation of the concept of love can be independently researched by studying the Uzbek and English literature on this topic. This can be explored through love content, terms, metaphors and other expressive means of language . This helps to explain people's thoughts, emotions and behavior and communication processes .

Key words: concept of love, love, brightness, respect, trust, regret, lingocognitive, lingo-philosophical interpretation.

Introduction: Although the concept of love is expressed in Uzbek and English languages with lingo-philosophical and lingo-cognitive interpretation, various scientific explanations are used in the issues of their correctness and precise definition.

One of the lingo-philosophical (philosophy of language) definitions defines love as "a feeling of personal closeness, love, respect and its inseparability" and emphasizes that this concept is important in human relations, language and spirituality .

The lingocognitive (linguistic-spiritual) level reflects the connection of the concept of love with the spiritual world of a person. In this context, love refers to an emotional problem expressed through language.

Also, the interpretation of "love" in the Uzbek language is related to the words expressing this concept (love, respect, brightness). English words such as "love", "affection", "tenderness" represent the lingo-philosophical and lingo-cognitive aspects of love. The following words are used to express the lingo-philosophical and lingo-cognitive interpretation of the concept of love in Uzbek and English:

In Uzbek:

- Love: The feeling of making someone happy and happy , in a glorious, long-term relationship
- Respect: Showing appreciation, love and attention
- Radiance: Showing care and dignity
- Confidence: Proving, disputing
- Regret: An insight or confession

In English:

- Love: A deep affection for someone or something
- Affection: A gentle feeling of fondness or liking
- Tenderness: Showing care and gentleness towards someone
- Respect: Admiration for someone based on their abilities, qualities or achievements
- Trust: Firm belief in the reliability, truth, ability, or strength of someone or something

These words represent the lingo-philosophical (philosophy of language) and lingo-cognitive (cognitive processes related to language and its meanings) interpretation of the concept of love.

The main part: Let's talk about the importance of the lingo-philosophical and lingo-cognitive interpretation of the concept of love . Lingophilosophy is a scientific discipline that seeks to study the logical relationships between languages , thinking and analyzing meanings. Lingocognitivism focuses on the study of meanings between languages, their formation and thought-logical processes.

can also be independently researched by studying the Uzbek and English literature on this topic . This can be explored through love content, terms, metaphors and other expressive means of language . This helps to explain people's thoughts, emotions and behavior and communication processes .

of the concept of love in Uzbek and English languages is very important. This concept is one of the most important and basic emotions for people and includes important ways of expressing it through language, understanding it, describing it and describing it .

Lingophilosophical (philosophy of language) interpretation represents the logical or philosophical dimension of philosophy related to the basic rules of interpreting the concept of love through language and its meanings. Through this interpretation, the logical tools of language are used to think about love, analyze its aspects, and describe it.

Lingocognitive (language-meaning connection) interpretation allows the processes of understanding, describing and classifying meanings through language. This process involves thinking about the origins of the concept of love, the words, phrases and phrases used to describe it .

correct people's strange thoughts about love, help them solve their problems in cooperation with other people . It also provides a basis for more lessons in human relations through these interpretations .

of the concept of love in Uzbek and English languages is very important. These concepts are fundamental in understanding human interactions and worldviews, and the importance of language in their expression is very high.

Lingo-philosophical interpretation includes the study of the expression of the concept through language and the philosophical acute processes related to its meanings. Through this interpretation, it will be possible to understand the true meaning of the concept of love, its manifestations and opinions about its worldview.

Lingocognitive interpretation aims to study the relationship between language and its meanings and master concepts . Through this method, it is possible to develop knowledge about the different aspects of the concept of love , its perspectives and its tariffs.

With the help of these interpretations, people can clearly define the concept of love, communicate it to other people and understand its importance. Such linguistic methods help to deepen the understanding of fundamental issues such as love and are organically rich in human relationships .

Lingo-philosophical and lingo-cognitive definitions of the concept of love in Uzbek and English are as follows :

Lingo-philosophical: Love is defined as a set of human preferences that express the human spirit, emotions and existence . These advantages may consist of love, respect, love, dignity, honor and others .

Lingocognitive: Love is concerned with how one understands oneself in relation to one's inner and outer world . These concepts grow even when a person is not interacting with people and influence his actions and thoughts.

In English, the word "love" means love. In lingo-philosophical terms, love means a person's respect for other persons , helping them and appreciating them. And in the lingocognitive tariff, love is known as a strong feeling, which usually falls on something or someone . Love is expressed by different words in Uzbek and

English languages . It is used as "love" or "mehr-muhabbat" in Uzbek, while the word "love" is used in English. The importance and meaning of love is similar in both languages , but may be emphasized differently depending on cultural and social norms.

Uzbek, love is usually associated with values such as family, friendship, and respect, while in English, there is a concept focused on romantic relationships. Therefore, the expression of the concept of love in both languages may reflect cultural differences .

Also, similar metaphors and idioms are used to express love in both languages. For example, expressions such as "my heart beats with you" or " you are the apple of my eye " are often used in an emotional context. As a result , the expression of the concept of love in both languages is shaped by differences in cultural and emotional contexts. Studying this issue can help to better understand the concept of love in both languages.

Discussion : To express the concept of love in the Uzbek language, the following phraseological unit with the participation of body parts components is also used: to hit the liver (to fall in love) [3 ; B. 269]. In English, somatisms expressing the concept of love with the "liver" component were not found. Most Uzbek and English proverbs about love reflect the emotional interest of opposite sexes. proverbs such as "a house looks like a house", "Love lives in cottages as well as in courts" can also be included in this semantic group. In these proverbs, it is expressed that even a hut can become a paradise with love, that is, poverty cannot be an obstacle to it. But there are also English proverbs that contradict this semantic meaning , for example, "When poverty comes in at the door, love flies out at the window", it is observed that the feeling of mutual love is lost due to poverty. In the Uzbek equivalent of the proverb "A person who comes by himself, a person who leaves on his own", the reason for the departure of a person is not shown to be financial difficulties. In Uzbek proverbs, we can see that love is not dependent on material wealth, it is a beautiful divine feeling, and it is priceless and it is not easy to achieve it. Pure love cannot be sold or thrown away; love cannot be sold in the market; love cannot be bought for money, heart cannot be bought for money; love is not equal to wealth The following English proverbs emphasize that love is a powerful emotion: Love is blind; Absence makes the heart grow fonder; Faults are thick where love is thin; Love makes the world go round.

Conclusion In this short article, the difference between the concept of "love" in Uzbek and English languages was discussed. In Uzbek, the term "love" or "love" is associated with values such as family, friendship, and respect, and in English, it means focusing on romantic relationships. At the same time, the metaphors and expressions used to express love in both languages are similar. For example, expressions such as "my heart beats with you" or "you are not in my eyes" are popular in the context of many ideas. For more details of these, it may help to better understand the concept of love in both languages.

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